

Analysis of relationship between rainfall anomaly and SST Nino 3.4 anomaly for determination of key areas of Indonesia's climate diversity to support climate change adaptations on agricultural sector

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ABSTRACT

The vast territory of Indonesia and its position flanked by two oceans and two continents make the Indonesia's climate very dynamic and complex. On the other hand, climate variability and its change continue to occur and the impacts vary signifikan in agriculture sector. The pattern and tendency of climate variability can be detected through global indices such as Nino 3.4 sea surface temperature (SST) and its relationship to rainfall anomalies. Rainfall is one of the climate parameters that most plays a role in agriculture. The most obvious impact of climate change on the agricultural sector is the reduction in planting area and the decrease in production. Therefore, the Agriculture Sector needs to make adaptation efforts to reduce the risk due to climate change. This paper presents the results of the analysis of the relationship between Nino 3.4 SST anomalies with rainfall anomalies to determine the key regions of Indonesia's climate diversity. Key Areas were identified based on the correlation more than 0.5 and less than -0.5 significance less than 0.1 of the Niño 3.4 SST index with rainfall anomalies. The results of the analysis show that every condition in both El-Niño and La-Niña has a different lag and global index where the correlation is strong and significant. Key areas have been identified in El-Niño and La-Niña condition. These regions are areas that are significantly affected by climate variability and have an impact on rainfall anomalies which will ultimately affect the agricultural sector.

Keywords: *Key Area, rainfall anomaly, SST Niño 3.4 anomaly, El-Niño, La-Niña*

INTRODUCTION

The impact of climate change on the agricultural sector is very significant both directly and indirectly. Some research results state the impact of climate change on the food crops (Taweessin, et al. 2019, Stueker et al. 2018, Nimusiin et al. 2018, Ajithkumar et al. 2018, Md Abiar et al. 2017, Ndamani et al. 2014 and Aninagyei et al. 2014). Climate anomalies that are also an important part of the phenomenon of climate change greatly affect rainfall in Indonesia. The relationship between climate and rainfall was also examined by Claudia et al. (2018) by taking the study at Bolivian Altiplano. The phenomenon of climate

change and its impact has accelerated in recent decades (Sheffield and Wood, 2011). Developed countries today are better able to manage the impacts of a variable climate, but in developing countries the increasing frequency and magnitude of extreme weather events pose potentially disastrous consequences for agriculture and food security (Field 2000, Wilhite 2005, Sheffield and Wood, 2011, Sivakumaretal. 2011a). Knowledge of how and where the climate has varied and is changing is crucial to developing successful coping strategies for agriculture and eco-systems in general (Heim Jr., 2015).

The climate anomaly phenomenon that often occurs is El-Niño and La-Niña. The results of Las (2003), which analyzed rainfall data from 239 stations in Java and Bali, having the observation period of more than 30 years, showed that, in La-Niña, almost all stations had higher annual rainfall (112-131%) than the climatological normal. In contrast, in El-Niño, almost all stations had lower rainfall (79.3-86.2%) than the climatological normal. Climate anomalies not only affect the amount of rainfall, but also the pattern and duration of periods of rain and drought which have implications for the shifting of the planting season (Las 2003).

The influence of climate anomalies on rainfall looks typical and varies in each region. This means that the size of the effect is closely related to local characteristics and conditions in the area in question. The clearer the rain pattern that occurs in an area, the influence of climate anomaly will also be seen clearly and this will facilitate the analysis of the data. According to Las (2004), the magnitude of the effect of climate anomalies on Indonesia's rainfall is determined by three factors, namely: 1) equatorial position related to the role of the trade wind, 2) monsoonal influence in relation to the role of monsoon winds, especially the western monsoon, and 3) local influences especially topographic, mountainous, hydrological and other aspects.

Changes in patterns, intensity and distribution of rainfall are very influential on agricultural activities, especially cultivation of plants. While the pattern, intensity and distribution of rainfall are strongly influenced by global mechanisms and cycles such as sea surface temperature. One of the most commonly used global indices to see its relationship to rainfall in Indonesia is Nino 3.4 sea surface temperature. Some research results showed a correlation between Sea Surface Temperature (SST) and rainfall. Based on the results of Hendon (2003), it is known that Nino 3.4 SST variability affects 50% of rainfall variations across Indonesia while the SST variability in the Indian Sea is 10-15%. In the dry season, SST anomalies that reach +1oC have caused rainfall to fall below normal. With Indonesian rainfall data and Indo Pacific SST period 1951-1997, Aldrian and Susanto (2003) concluded that rainfall anomalies in the dry season were coherent and strongly correlated with ENSO variations in the

Pacific, whereas the correlation was weak in the rainy season. The results of Roberts et al. (2014) in Luzon, the Philippines, showed that variations in average July–September Niño-3.4 SSTAs explained approximately 29% of the interannual variations in the deviations of total January–June (dry season) rice production from a polynomial trend for 1970–2005. In contrast, no impact was found on July–December production in either year t or $t + 1$. The impact of ENSO on dry-season rice production in Luzon appeared to be primarily due to changes in area harvested rather than yield. Production declines for rainfed ecosystems were relatively larger than those for irrigated ecosystems: a 1°C increase in average July–September Niño-3.4 SSTA was associated with a 3.7% decrease in irrigated dry-season production but with a 13.7% decline in rainfed dry-season production.

More intensive research to study rainfall response to SST was carried out by Aldrian and Susanto (2003) by correlating seasonal rainfall with Indonesian oceanic SST to Niño 3.4. The results of the analysis showed that the influence of SST varied for each season and every rainy region. A fairly high correlation (0.45–0.7) occurred in the June–November period in each rainy region. This means that the correlation is more real in the dry season. The same conclusion was also obtained from the results of Las's study (2004) which states that the correlation of rainfall anomalies with SST anomalies in many parts of Indonesia was more significant in the dry season than in the rainy season. Related to the correlation, Boer (1999) and Ratag (1997) showed that the correlation between the observation pattern and output of various models for the Indonesian region was around 0.6–0.8 for air temperature and around 0.4–0.5 for rainfall.

The purpose of this paper is to give the information about regions in Indonesia which have a strong and significant correlation between SST in Niño 3.4 and rainfall anomalies. Data and information are expected to help policy makers in determining priority areas related to programs and actions for adaptation to climate change.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The pattern of the relationship between global indices and the incidence of rain was the basis of the analysis in this paper. The monthly rainfall data used a period of more than 20 years from 621 rain stations. Rainfall data is obtained from Berau of Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics (BMKG), Ministry of Public Work and Indonesian Agroclimate and Hydrology Research Institute (IAHRI). For global index data used was Niño 3.4 sea surface temperature anomaly data, obtained from the NOAA web.

The Niño 3.4 region was an overlap of some of the Niño 3 and Niño 4 regions. The boundaries were 5o LU - 5o LS and 170o - 120o BB (Figure 1). Niño 3.4 was defined by Barnston et al. (1997) when they founded that Niño 3.4

had a better correlation with ENSO events compared to Niño 3. If sea surface temperature anomaly (Sea Surface Temperature Anomaly (SSTA) in Niño 3.4 had a value of $\geq + 0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$, then it was categorized as El-Niño. Whereas La-Niña occurred when SSTA had a value of $\leq - 0.4^{\circ}\text{C}$ (Trenberth, 1997).

Picture 1. Niño 3.4 observation area (Source: NOAA)

Rainfall data was then calculated for anomalies. The value of rainfall anomaly at an observation point in a particular month is the difference between the value of observations in a particular month with the average value of the same month from the observations during the data period.

$$\Delta Y_{ij} = Y_{ij} - \bar{Y}_j \quad \bar{Y}_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n Y_{ij}}{N_j}$$

Y_j is the average value of rainfall in the j-month, Y_{ij} is the rainfall data for the j-month on the i-observation, ΔY_{ij} is the rainfall of the j-month in the i-observation, and N_j is the number of observations for j-month rainfall.

The next step was determination of the lag in rainfall anomaly data and the Niño 3.4 SST index. Lag is time difference (in months) between SST Niño 3.4 anomalies and rainfall anomalies. Lag 1 means that the rainfall anomaly this month was influenced by Niño 3.4 SST in the previous month. Lag 2 means that this month's rainfall anomaly is influenced by Niño 3.4 SST anomalies in the previous 2 months, and so on until lag 4. The next, data were sorted for normal conditions, El-Niño and La-Niña. Likewise, the Niño 3.4 SST index data were sorted and adjusted periodically with rainfall anomaly data. In this study the determination of key areas of climate diversity was determined at correlation values > 0.5 and < -0.5 , and $p < 0.1$ (90% confidence level).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The result of the correlation between rainfall anomalies and SST Nino 3.4 anomalies in El-Niño conditions showed that in general strong correlation values (r) were more scattered in lag 2 (Figure 1). The rain stations with strong correlation (0.4-0.6) are Sekincau, Cigudeg, Jiken, Bakung, Sintang, Pangkalanbun and Moanamani, while the strong negative correlation (<-0.4) are Detusoko, Juntinyuat, Subang, Ringinharjo, Palasasri, Kambat, Sepingga, Anggana and Tanah Grogot (Table 1).

Figure 1. Correlation map between rainfall anomaly and Nino 3.4 index in El-Niño condition

Table 1. List of rainfall stasiun with high correlation and signifikan in El-Nino condition

CORRELATION	PROVINCE	DISTRICT	STATION	r value
0.4-0.6	LAMPUNG	Lampung Barat	StaSekincau	0,461
0.4-0.6	JAWA BARAT	Bogor	Cigudeg	0,425
0.4-0.6	JAWA TENGAH	Blora	StaJIKEN	0,594
0.4-0.6	JAWA TIMUR	Kediri	Bakung	0,405
0.4-0.6	KALIMANTAN BARAT	Pontianak	Stasiun Meteorologi Sintang	0,462
0.4-0.6	KALIMANTAN TENGAH	Kotawaringin Barat	Sta Pangkalanbun	0,566
0.4-0.6	PAPUA	Nabire	Sta. Met. Kelas III Moanamani	0,585
-0.8--0.6	NTT	Ende	Detusoko	-0,693
-0.6--0.4	JAWA BARAT	Indramayu	Juntinyuat	-0,445
-0.6--0.4	JAWA BARAT	Subang	Subang	-0,542
-0.6--0.4	DIY	Bantul	StaRINGINHAR	-0,43
-0.6--0.4	BALI	Jembrana	Palasasri	-0,562
-0.6--0.4	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	Hulu Sungai Tengah	Stasiun KAMBAT	-0,454
-0.6--0.4	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	Balipapan	Sta. Met. Kelas I Sultan A.M.S Sepingga	-0,448
-0.6--0.4	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	Kutai Kartanegara	Anggana	-0,401
-0.6--0.4	KALIMANTAN TIMUR	Paser	Tanah Grogot	-0,511

In La-Niñacondition, the area with strong and significant correlation values (r) was greater in lag 2 (Figure 2). The stations with a correlation of more than 0.4 or less than -0.4 are South Lampung, Bogor, Tangerang and Tabalong (Table 2).

Figure 2. Correlation map between rainfall anomaly and Nino 3.4 index in La-Niña condition

Table 2. List of rainfall stasiun with high correlation and signifikan in La-Nina condition

CLASS-CORRELATION	PROVINCE	KABUPATEN	STATION	r VALUE
0.4-0.6	LAMPUNG	Lampung Selatan	StaMetrodpu	0,515
0.4-0.6	JAWA BARAT	Bogor	Cigudeg	0,451
0.4-0.6	JAWA BARAT	Bogor	Dayeuh	0,589
0.4-0.6	BANTEN	Tangerang	Cikasunga	0,442
-0.6--0.4	KALIMANTAN SELATAN	Tabalong	Stasiun Haruai Muui	-0,532

For a significance value of less than 0.1 based on the distribution map (Figure 3) it is seen most in lag 3. There are 162 rain stations from 621 stations (26%) which have a p value of less than 0.1 or very real/significant. The significance value explains that Nino 3.4 SST anomalies significantly affect rainfall anomalies. The location that shows the most significant number of stations is East Java Province, namely 38 stations and East Kalimantan 20 stations. The complete data is presented in Appendix Table 1.

Figure 3. Significance map between rainfall anomaly and Nino 3.4 index in El-Niño condition

Figure 4. Significance map between rainfall anomaly and Niño 3.4 index in La-Niña condition

Key area of Indonesia's climate diversity was determined based on the results of strong correlation and significance between rainfall anomalies and SST Niño 3.4 anomalies. In this paper, strong correlation values were set more than 0.5 or less than -0.5 and significant level with a confidence level of less than 0.1 (90% real level).

The results of the identification selected 4 Key Area for El-Niño conditions: 1). Pangkalanbun Station in Kotawaringin Barat District, Central Kalimantan Province, 2). Class III Meteorology Station Moanamani in Nabire Regency, Papua Province, 3). Detusoko Station, Ende Regency, East Nusa Tenggara Province (NTT), 4) Gorontalo Station, Gorontalo Regency, Gorontalo Province. The lag of each location varied from 2 to 4 (Table 3). The resulting correlation values ranged from 0.57 to 0.59 and -0.55 to -0.55 with a significance level of 0 to 0.03 (very significant). Negative correlation illustrates that an increase in SST anomalies in Niño 3.4 affects the decrease in rainfall. This happened at the location of Detusoko Station and Gorontalo Station. On the other hand, for positive correlations, it will affect the increase in rainfall, such as at Pangkalanbun Station at lag 2 and Moanamani Station at lags 2, 3 and 4. The distribution of those stations can be seen in Figure 5.

Table 3. Key area in El-Nino conditions

Condition	Location	District	Province	Lag	Correlation	Significance
El Nino	Sta. Pangkalanbun	Kotawaringin Barat	Kalteng	2	0.57	0.01
	Sta. Met Kelas III Moanamani	Nabire	Papua	2	0.58	0
	Sta. Detusoko	Ende	NTT	2	-0.69	0.01
	Sta. Met Kelas III Moanamani	Nabire	Papua	3	0.59	0
	Sta. Gorontalo	Gorontalo	Gorontalo	4	-0.55	0.03
	Sta. Met Kelas III Moanamani	Nabire	Papua	4	0.58	0

Figure 5. Map of Key Area Indonesia’s Climate Variability based on correlation and significance between rainfall anomaly and Nino 3.4 index in El-Niño condition

In La-Niñacondition, there were 3 Key Area that had a high and significant correlation between Nino 3.4 SST anomalies and rainfall anomalies at lag 1, 2, 3 and 4. The three locations included: 1). Taman Roya Station, Jeneponto Regency, South Sulawesi Province, 2). HaruaiMuui Station, Tabalong Regency, South Kalimantan Province and 3). Cigudeg Station, Bogor Regency, West Java Province (Table 4). All locations showed a negative correlation, meaning that an increase in Nino 3.4 SST anomalies hadan impact on decreasing rainfall, or a decrease inNino 3.4 SST anomalies hadan impact on increasing rainfall. In the La-Niñaphenomenon, generally, there is a condition where Nino 3.4 SST anomaly decreases (index < -0.4), so that it has an impact on increasing rainfall. The distribution of thelocations can be seen on the map in Figure 6.

Table 4. Key area in La-Nina conditions

CONDITION	LOCATION	DISTRICT	PROVINCE	LAG	CORRELATION	SIGNIFICANCE
La Nina	Sta. Taman Roya	Jeneponto	Sulsel	1	-1	0.06
	Sta. Taman Roya	Jeneponto	Sulsel	2	-1	0.14
	Sta. Haruai Muui	Tabalong	Kalsel	2	-0.53	0
	Sta. Taman Roya	Jeneponto	Sulsel	3	-1	0.06
	Sta. Cigudeg	Bogor	Jabar	3	-0.56	0
	Sta. Taman Roya	Jeneponto	Sulsel	4	-1	0
	Sta. Haruai Muui	Tabalong	Kalsel	4	-0.53	0

Figure 6. Map of Key Area Indonesia’s Climate Variability based on correlation and significance between rainfall anomaly and Nino 3.4 index in La-Niña condition

The distribution of correlation values and significance showed that the influence of Nino 3.4 SST anomalies on rainfall anomalies in Indonesia was quite diverse. There was a strong, medium and weak correlation and significant, very significant or insignificant distribution. Therefore, an analysis is needed to find out which areas have strong and significant correlations. Areas that have been identified as key regions mean that rainfall anomalies in the regions are strongly influenced by Nino 3.4 SST anomalies at certain lags. Nino 3.4 SST anomaly is a strong indicator to predict rainfall in the key area. Monitoring of Nino 3.4 SST anomalies on a regular and continuous basis will be very helpful to find out the possibility of anomalies of rainfall/climate extrem that will occur. The

identification of this key area is expected to help in determining priority areas for monitoring extrim climate impact on agriculture sector.

CONCLUSION

Differences of time lag between the occurrence of rainfall anomalies and the Nino 3.4 index affected the strength of the correlation and significance.

In El-Niño conditions, time lags 2, 3 and 4 had a strong correlation between rainfall anomaly and SST Nino 3.4. Key areas were Kotawaringin Barat, Ende, Gorontalo, Nabire and Mimika.

In La-Niña conditions, time lag 1, 2, 3 and 4 had a strong correlation between rainfall anomaly and SST Nino 3.4. Key Area are Bogor, Tabalong and Jenepono.

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